

IMPLEMENTATION OF GOOD GOVERNANCE AND ITS EFFECT ON LOCAL GOVERNMENT TRANSPARENCY

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the effect of the application of Good Governance principles on local government transparency. In the context of good governance, principles such as accountability, participation, transparency, responsiveness, efficiency and equality are decisive factors in improving the quality of public services and public trust. This study uncovers the extent to which good governance practices contribute to improving local government transparency, which is one of the main factors in promoting democracy and sustainable socio-economic development. This study used a qualitative approach with a literature research method. This study found that the implementation of good governance has a significant influence on local government transparency. Good governance principles such as public participation, accountability, and transparency are proven to improve the quality of information provided to the public, facilitate social monitoring, and strengthen public trust in government institutions.

Keywords: Implementation, Good Governance, Transparency, Local Government.

Introduction

Transparency in local government is an important component that determines the level of public trust and the effectiveness and accountability of government. The importance of transparency has been recognized around the world as a key indicator of good governance (Aguilera, R. V., & Cuervo-Cazurra, A. 2009). Transparency allows the public to access information about policies, decision-making, and the allocation of public funds, all of which lead to community empowerment and more effective government oversight (Addink, H. 2019).

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However, challenges continue to be faced in the quest to improve local government transparency. Issues that hinder democratic processes and efficient governance (Sundaram, J. K., & Chowdhury, A. (Eds.). 2012). One of the main challenges is the unavailability of adequate public information, where strategic documents, financial reports, and information on decision-making are often difficult for the public to access. This not only creates a sense of mistrust from citizens towards the government, but also makes it difficult for people to participate in the decision-making process and public oversight that is the foundation of a healthy democratic system (Keping, Y. 2018).

Furthermore, transparency issues are also often linked to corruption and nepotism practices that can be entrenched in the local government system. These behaviors threaten the integrity of government and reduce effectiveness and efficiency in providing public services. This lack of transparency reflects the weak implementation of the principle of accountability in governance, where local government officials and local politicians are sometimes able to manipulate the system for personal or group interests without having to account for their actions to the public (Rotberg, R. I. 2014). As a result, the struggle to maximize transparency in government is a constant struggle and requires a systematic and integrated approach to address the problem (Thomas, G. W. 2012).

To address the issue of transparency in local government, a number of periodic efforts need to be intensified. The first step is to strengthen regulations that support access to public information, including ensuring that all government processes and decisions are accessible, monitored and evaluated by the public (De Vries, M. S. 2013). This requires local governments to adopt policies that facilitate information disclosure, such as providing key documents in easily accessible online portals and holding public forums for open discussions between officials and citizens (Graham et al., 2003).

It is also important for local governments to instill a culture of integrity and accountability among state civil servants. Training and educating government employees on the importance of transparency and adherence to good governance principles can help build a shared understanding and commitment to responsible public service delivery (Nag, N. S. 2018). These initiatives should be combined with the implementation of an effective oversight system that involves independent oversight institutions as well as the active participation of civil society and the media in monitoring government activities (Gisselquist, R. M. 2012).

The development of public complaint mechanisms and a legally protected whistleblower system can also be an important part of efforts to increase transparency and reduce the potential for corruption in local government (Huther, J., & Shah, A. 2005). Through these mechanisms, citizens can play a direct role in exposing injustices and abuses of power that may occur. These efforts, if implemented consistently and sustainably, will not only increase transparency in local government but also restore

public trust and improve the efficiency and efficacy of public services in general (Rothstein, B. 2012).

Therefore, the importance of the concept of good governance offers a framework for governance reform that involves principles such as accountability, transparency, participation, effectiveness and efficiency, and fairness.

Through the application of good governance principles, it is expected that a local government can not only increase transparency but also improve the quality of public services and strengthen the relationship between the government and its people. The application of good governance, if implemented effectively, has great potential in creating a government system that is responsive and accountable to the needs and aspirations of the people (Smith, B. 2007).

Therefore, it is important to examine and analyze the extent to which the implementation of good governance principles in local governments has contributed to increased transparency. This study aims to investigate the relationship between the implementation of good governance and the level of transparency in local government, with the hope that the results can provide concrete recommendations for improving transparency and accountability in local government in the future.

Research Method

The research method conducted in this study is literature. The literature research method is an analytical approach that focuses on collecting, identifying, and analyzing data or information from various literature sources relevant to the research topic (Champe & Kleist, 2003). Typical stages of literature research include searching for relevant keywords in catalogs, indexes, and search engines to identify appropriate sources. The sources explored can vary from books, journal articles, magazines, to online sources related to the research problem and objectives (Boddy, 2016).

This method allows researchers to gain a broader and more in-depth view of the topic under study without having to conduct primary data collection. In addition, literature studies also play an important role in determining existing research gaps, allowing future research to focus more on unexplored areas or those that still require further proof (Christensen et al., 2011; Lancaster, 2007).

Result and Discussion

Good Governance and transparency

Good Governance, in essence, is a concept of government that builds and applies the principles of professionalism, democracy, transparency, efficiency, accountability, effectiveness, excellent service, and is acceptable to the entire community (Andrews, M. 2008). Good governance is government management that is solid, accountable, and based on the principles of openness and justice (Aguilera, R. V., & Cuervo-Cazurra, A. 2009).

Meanwhile, transparency in the context of good governance means the creation of openness in policies and their implementation, so that the public's rights to information on government decisions are more secure. Transparency is key to ensuring that government actions and policies can be accessed and assessed by the public, thereby increasing accountability and public trust in government (Börzel et al., 2008).

Good governance is a basic principle in effective, efficient and accountable governance. The following are some of the main principles of good governance: 1) **Accountability:** Accountability is the government's obligation to report and be accountable for its work to the public. This principle demands a transparent and verifiable process so that all parts of government, be it the executive, legislature or judiciary, must be able to explain and account for their actions to the public. Accountability is the foundation of people's trust in their government. 2) **Transparency:** Transparency means that information should be available and accessible to the public, and that decisions and policies are made openly and following the rules. It allows citizens to have access to the information they need to participate effectively in the decision-making process. Without transparency, it is difficult for people to have confidence in public management and governance. 3) **Participation:** Participation refers to the involvement of people in the decision-making process. It includes all levels of society including marginalized groups and cannot discriminate based on gender, race, religion, or socio-economic status. Participation can be direct or through authorized representatives. Public participation in governance helps strengthen accountability and transparency and improves policy performance and outcomes. 4) **Effectiveness and Efficiency:** This principle underscores the importance of government producing results that meet people's needs while making optimal use of resources. Efficiency in the use of fiscal resources, natural resources, human resources, etc., is key to the effectiveness of good governance. Efficiency and effectiveness involve managing resources to ensure that the outcomes of the use of those resources provide maximum benefits to society. 5) **Equity and Inclusiveness:** The principles of equity and justice require government to serve all its citizens fairly and without discrimination. Every citizen should have equal opportunities to access public services and participate in economic, political and social activities. A good government ensures that the human rights and basic freedoms of every individual are legally protected. 6) **Rule of Law:** The principle of the rule of law emphasizes the importance of law in guiding the behavior of society and government. Laws must be enforced fairly and indiscriminately, ensuring that every individual enjoys equal protection before the law. Consistent and fair law enforcement promotes stability and certainty, and ensures that everyone's rights and obligations are upheld to prevent abuse of power and corruption. 7) **Responsiveness:** A responsive government listens to the needs and aspirations of its people and acts to respond in a timely manner. Recognizing and adapting to people's changing circumstances or priorities is key to ensuring that services and policies are designed to meet their actual needs. This

responsiveness strengthens the relationship between the government and its citizens, which in turn increases public trust. 8) Strategic Vision: Leaders in government must have a long-term vision for the progress and well-being of the people they serve. They should be able to formulate and implement policies and strategies that reflect the long-term interests of the people, not just short-term interests or political gain. This strategic vision also includes an understanding of the complexities of the modern world and the flexibility to adapt to emerging challenges. 9) Consensus-Oriented: Democracy is not just about the majority winning votes, but also about seeking the best consensus that enables a broad and deep understanding of the interests of different groups in a society. Efforts to reach consensus in decision-making help minimize conflict and strengthen the legitimacy of government policies and programs (Addink, H. 2019; Botchway, F. N. 2000; Sundaram, J. K., & Chowdhury, A. (Eds.). 2012; Denters et al., 2023).

Good Governance ensures that democratic principles are applied and safeguarded, policy-making processes are approached in a moral, legal, and ethical manner, and government effectively serves and protects the interests of all its citizens.

Good Governance is a paradigm built on a framework of democratic principles and efficient management, realizing a system of government that is transparent, accountable and serves the public interest fairly (Dellepiane-Avellaneda, S. 2010). The concept values public participation in the development process, pursues efficiency, and operates within the scope of a strong legal framework. By implementing Good Governance, the government is expected to create a political, social, and economic environment conducive to sustainable growth and development, and improve the quality of life of the people (Keping, Y. 2018). The key to successful Good Governance lies in the balance between a strong and accountable government and an active and informed society that is able to participate in the development of its country (Nanda, V. P. 2006).

The Effect of Good Governance Implementation on Local Government Transparency

The implementation of good governance has a significant influence in increasing transparency at the local government level (Besançon, M. 2003). With the principle of accountability, local governments are required to provide information about political decisions, resource allocation, and budget management to citizens in an open and accessible manner. This practice allows citizens to gain a clearer understanding of how funds and other resources are used (Rotberg, R. I. 2014). This, in turn, strengthens public trust in local governments, as a basis for legitimizing the policies and programs they implement.

Furthermore, with increased transparency resulting from the implementation of good governance, citizens have greater opportunities to participate in the decision-making process (Rose-Ackerman, S. 2017). Platforms such as public hearings, utilization of information technology for example through government websites or social media,

and good accountability systems allow citizens to provide feedback and suggestions on plans and policies that are being discussed or have been implemented (Sharma, S. D. 2007). Thus, transparent local governments not only enable but also encourage active citizen engagement, which is an essential element in the management of a healthy and inclusive democracy.

Finally, transparency that results from good governance plays a role in the prevention of corruption and the enhancement of quality local resource management. When decision-making processes, procurement of goods and services, and budget governance are carried out openly, opportunities for fraud can be minimized (Esty, D. C. 2005). This is because there is direct supervision from the public as well as non-governmental organizations and the media that can provide social control. This preventive action supported by transparency results in better and more accountable financial management, ensuring that local resources are used to maximize community welfare in a fair and equitable manner (Newell, R., & Wilson, G. 2002).

Good governance practices that prioritize transparency in local government also contribute to the creation of a more efficient and effective governance environment (Grindle, M. S. 2007). With strong transparency practices, local governments are required to be more careful in the planning and execution of their programs, ensuring that every decision and budget allocation can be accounted for. This encourages more efficient use of resources, avoidance of budget waste, and selection and implementation of programs that are well-targeted according to the needs of the community (Thomas, G. W. 2012). Thus, transparency not only reduces the potential for abuse of power but also optimizes the distribution of resources for public welfare.

On the other hand, increased transparency and public participation in decision-making results in more inclusive and diverse policies and programs. With more inputs and perspectives from different walks of life in the policy-making process, the result is policies that are more balanced and representative of the needs and aspirations of the wider community (Kaufmann et al, 2000). This not only perpetuates the legitimacy of the policies made but also increases their effectiveness, as people are more likely to support and participate in the implementation of policies that they feel they have contributed to making (Grindle, M. S. 2011).

Thus, the implementation of good governance and transparency in local government brings significant changes to the way government is run. The domino effect extends from increased accountability and reduced corruption, to the creation of more inclusive policies and more effective program implementation. By supporting active citizen engagement in governance processes and optimizing resource management, local governments can ensure sustainable growth and development and more equitable prosperity for all.

A conceptual model linking the implementation of good governance with the level of local government transparency

The conceptual model linking the implementation of good governance with the level of local government transparency can be represented in several interrelated dimensions (De Vries, M. S. 2013). Initially, the model focuses on the basic principles of good governance, such as accountability, responsiveness, equality and participation. In relation to transparency, the principle of accountability requires local governments to answer for their decisions and actions, ensuring that policies are made and implemented in a way that is clear and accountable to the public (Kjaer, A. M. 2023). Meanwhile, the principle of participation emphasizes the importance of public involvement in decision-making processes, which is directly related to transparency; people must have easy access to information in order to participate effectively. These two principles, along with others, interact to improve local government transparency, through the implementation of open and clear policies contained in official documents, the creation of easily accessible data, and active communication between the government and the public (Handayani, F. A., & Nur, M. I. 2019).

Furthermore, this conceptual model reflects how increased transparency, as a result of implementing good governance, positively affects other important aspects of good government. Improved transparency provides the basis for stronger public oversight and corruption prevention. This creates a virtuous feedback cycle where increased transparency brings success in the implementation of good governance, which in turn strengthens transparency even further (Okot-Uma, R. W. O., & London, C. S. 2000). This effect creates a more responsive governance environment, where the public can more easily evaluate and provide feedback on government decisions, thus promoting continuous improvement in the quality of public services. Thus, this conceptual model shows that the implementation of good governance and increased transparency go hand in hand, each reinforcing and strengthening the other in an effort to create better and more accountable government (Shattock, M. 2006).

Furthermore, this conceptual model explains how improvements in transparency resulting from the implementation of good governance lead to the strengthening of local democracy. Transparency enables citizens to have access to information about government policies, decision-making, resource allocation and use, as well as the outcomes of implemented programs (Grindle, M. 2012). Access to this information is a key requirement for citizens to be able to participate actively and meaningfully in the democratic process, including in terms of monitoring and evaluating local government performance (Doornbos, M. 2003). This model implies that with increased transparency, local governments not only adhere to the principle of accountability, but also increase citizen engagement in governance, which is a key element of a healthy democracy. The provision of timely and accurate information helps

citizens to make more informed decisions, advocate for policies that support their interests, and demand improvements from local governments (Siddiqi et al., 2009).

At this point, the conceptual model summarizes the continuous improvement cycle between the implementation of good governance and the growth of transparency. As a result, an environment conducive to sustainable social and economic development is created. Transparency increases public trust in local governments, which is critical for social stability and economic investment (Akpan-Obong et al., 2023). Private investors and financial institutions are more willing to invest in areas where the government operates in an open and accountable manner, so transparency indirectly contributes to increased local economic development. On the other hand, stronger community involvement in government oversight promotes more efficient resource allocation and more effective policy implementation, all of which are key to addressing public concerns and improving people's quality of life (Zaitul et al., 2023). In this overall model, good governance and transparency are not only end goals, but also a continuous process that supports and strengthens democracy, economic growth, and social development (Sari, A. R. 2023).

Thus, good governance and transparency are not only essential components of effective governance, but also mutually reinforcing factors that work together to create a governance environment that is responsive, accountable, and respectful of the rights and voices of its citizens. Increased local government transparency as an expression of good governance can support the development of democracy, economic growth, and social welfare.

Conclusion

The implementation of good governance and its influence on local government transparency shows that good governance principles such as accountability, participation, equality, and responsiveness play an important role in increasing transparency in local government management. The implementation of these principles leads to the disclosure of information about decision-making, the use of resources, and the results achieved by local governments, which allows the public to gain access to relevant and accurate information. Good governance thus facilitates a more inclusive and participatory democratic process, where citizens can contribute to and oversee decision-making processes and policy implementation more effectively.

Furthermore, the findings confirm that increased transparency resulting from the implementation of good governance not only strengthens local democracy through broader community participation, but also contributes to sustainable economic and social development. Transparency increases public trust in government, which is key to social stability and attracting investment. This process creates a positive cycle of renewal in which the implementation of good governance and increased transparency reinforce each other, promoting a better environment for social and economic growth

while ensuring that government policies and programs reflect the needs and aspirations of the people.

Building on these findings, there are several important implications for local government practices to consider in their efforts to improve and develop the quality of governance. First, local governments should actively adopt and promote the principles of good governance, invest in systems that enable better access and dissemination of information to the public, and create mechanisms that are accountable and transparent. Furthermore, local governments should make continuous efforts to engage their citizens in decision-making processes, provide platforms for the public to participate constructively in dialog and policy-making, and proactively respond to their feedback and needs.

Second, the findings reinforce the need for convergence between technological innovation and good governance practices to support transparency. This includes the use of digital platforms and social media to strengthen communication links between local governments and communities, making governance processes more open and accessible. Through openness and a concerted effort to achieve Good Governance, local governments can demonstrate their commitment to people's welfare, strengthen institutional legitimacy and credibility, and promote more equitable and sustainable development. As such, the implementation of Good Governance is crucial to creating a healthy ecosystem of transparency, which in turn will affect not only public trust and participation, but also the overall performance and effectiveness of local governments.

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